

1979 – 2019

Contents

A few words	1
ESCP life	2
Articles & Reports	4
ESCP conferences	7
Announcements	8

ESCP

The tri-monthly newsletter
of the European Society
of Clinical Pharmacy

News

48th ESCP Symposium, 23-25 October 2019, Ljubljana (Slovenia)

The digital revolution: Supporting clinical pharmacy through e-health, digital support systems, big data and more!

General content of the conference, the country and the city

On behalf of the European Society of Clinical Pharmacy, we welcome you to the 48th ESCP conference, which will be held in Ljubljana, Slovenia, from 23 to 25th of October 2019. The theme of this year's symposium is "The Digital Revolution: supporting clinical pharmacy through e-health, digital support systems, big data and more." An indicative programme of topics will be addressed is as follows:

- General overview of the topic
- Direct patient care
- Tools to support clinical pharmacy
- Clinical decision support systems
- Big data etc.

Slovenia

Slovenia is a small but topographically diverse country in central Europe. The country, marked by a significant biodiversity, is one of the most water-rich in Europe, with a dense river network, a rich aquifer system, and significant Karst underground watercourses. Over half of the territory is covered by forest. The human settlement of Slovenia is dispersed and uneven. Slovenia covers 20,273 square kilometers and has a

population of 2.07 million and is known as an earthly paradise of snow-capped peaks, turquoise-green rivers and a Venetian-style coastline. Slovenia enriches its natural treasures with harmonious architecture, charming rustic culture and sophisticated cuisine.

Slovenia is one of the best undiscovered wine lands in the world, it has more than 28,000 wineries making between 80 and 90 million litres annually from the country's 22,300 ha of vineyards. Most of the country's wine production falls under the classification of premium wine with less than 30% classified as basic table wine. Slovenia is home of the oldest (450 years old) vine plant in the world.

Ljubljana and the Cankarjev dom

Ljubljana is the capital of Slovenia, it is a lively green city combining the charm of a small capital and the self-confidence of larger European cities. The image of the city by a river with picturesque bridges and a marketplace was designed by the famous architect Jože Plečnik. This city of a thou-

sand events is surrounded by parks and natural protected areas. The term "love" is in the name of Ljubljana itself, which sounds similar to "ljubljen(a)" (loved woman). Take a walk around the historical city centre, and explore all of its major attractions. Continue with a visit to Ljubljana Castle and treat yourself to beautiful views of the city from the castle's ramparts. In Ljubljana you have to visit Dragon Bridge, Ljubljana Castle and Central Market.

ESCP Conference will be held in Cankarjev dom, which is Slovenia's largest cultural institution, it was built between 1982 and 1983 to designs by the architect Edvard Ravnikar. Its numerous halls, connected by a large foyer on the upper floor and a smaller one on the lower floor, are used as venues for concerts, theatre performances, film screenings and conferences.

More about discovering Slovenia: <https://www.slovenia.info/en>

Alenka Kovačič
Chair of the 48th ESCP Symposium
alenka.kovacic@sb-ms.si

A Few Words

Dr Alenka Kovačič is a clinical pharmacy specialist, who has worked for more than 15 years in the Murska Sobota General Hospital, a regional hospital in the north-eastern part of Slovenia.

She works as a clinical pharmacist, mainly in the surgical and orthopaedic department of the hospital. Since 2013 she has been President of the Section of Clinical Pharmacists of Slovenia at the Slovenian Pharmaceutical Society. The Section of Clinical Pharmacists in Slovenia organizes several meetings annually and also one larger symposium each year.

Alenka is involved in the education program for pharmacists on the Faculty of Pharmacy in Ljubljana. She partly lectures on clinical pharmacy on the undergraduate level and partly on pharmacotherapy at postgraduate level. She also participates in various projects, one of which is, the develop-

ment of Telepharmacotherapy program in Slovenia. One of her greatest achievements was implementing a consultant clinical pharmacist to the primary level of health care across Slovenia, where she had a key role not just as a part of the first team of five clinical pharmacists, but as a leader in the final implementation on the national level.

From 2012-2015, Alenka was the coordinator of pharmacists' consultant program at the national level in the development task Quality Prescription of Medicines, which was supported from the Health Insurance Institute of Slovenia.

The development task was upgraded and incorporated in the national health care system on the primary level. At present, every patient with polypharmacy has a free access to a clinical pharmacist in every larger healthcare centre.

At the Slovene Chamber of Pharmacy, she is involved in the Competence Authority working group, where pharmaceutical cognitive services are being developed, and has been actively involved in the develop-

ment of the Pharmacotherapeutic Review in Slovenia. She was also a member of the Strategic Council for Medicines and the Health Council at the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Slovenia. For more than ten years, she has been a member of the Commission for the Classification of Medicines on the list at the Health Insurance Institute of Slovenia.

She is a co-mentor to many graduates at the Faculty of Pharmacy in Ljubljana and mentor to specialists in clinical pharmacy at the Slovene Chamber of Pharmacy.

She is an experienced speaker due to numerous lectures and speeches at meetings for healthcare professionals. In her profession she is especially dedicated to the optimisation of polypharmacotherapy for patients co-morbidities.

She has been a member of the ESCP for many years. She had already actively participated with posters and poster presentations on ESCP symposiums. This year she is president of the ESCP symposium, which will be held in Slovenia in Ljubljana from 23 to 25th of October 2019.

Who's who: Alenka Kovačič

Dr. Vibhu Paudyal is a Senior Lecturer in Clinical Pharmacy, University of Birmingham, UK. He is the deputy chair and member of the ESCP research committee.

He is also the associate editor of International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy and an editorial board member of Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy. He is the scientific committee member of the ESCP symposium in Ljubljana.

Dr Paudyal is a full time academic and researcher in Clinical Pharmacy and Pharmacy Practice and his research is focused on public health aspects of pharmacy practice.

He has led research and published widely in the area of self-care, patient access to medicines and medicine adherence. Populations of focus in his research include patients and users of clinical pharmacy services, persons experiencing homelessness, ethnic minorities and offshore workers.

Dr Paudyal was the recipient of the competitive ESCP research grant award in 2016. Through the grant award, the team consisting of collaborators from England, Scotland, Ireland and Malta systematically evaluated the evidence of pharmacy minor ailments management.

His research outputs in minor ailments research have been instrumental in changing policy and practice in the UK. Linked projects include evaluation of the early implementation of minor ailment service in the UK, comparative effectiveness of different models of care for minor ailments and systematic reviews.

Extending clinical pharmacy services to persons experiencing homelessness has been one of the focal areas of Dr Paudyal's research.

He has led work externally funded by Public Health England, National Health Service, UK and Universities in conducting health and pharmaceutical needs assessment, exploring multi-morbidity and barriers to medicines management in this population. He has also been involved in critical evaluation of national policies, pharmacist education and training, and establishing clinical pharmacy services for persons experiencing homelessness.

Such work has led to impactful publications in high ranking journals such as The Lancet and Br J Gen Practice.

Dr Paudyal is a keen enthusiast in clinical pharmacy and pharmacy practice education. He sits in the national evaluation steering committee of pharmacists' pre-registration training organised by Health Education England.

He has led innovative work in the evaluation and refinement of the recruitment methodology for pre-registration pharmacist training through externally funded work.

Dr Paudyal has led multiple workshop sessions aimed at pharmacy practice research methodology at ESCP symposiums since 2013. Dr Paudyal will be leading the ESCP Masterclass on 'the fundamentals of systematic reviews of clinical pharmacy innovations' at the ESCP symposium 2019 in Ljubljana.

Prior to his academic life, Dr Paudyal has worked as an industrial pharmacist. He has earned an MSc in Clinical Pharmacology and a PhD in Pharmacy Practice. He is a keen runner and recently completed London Marathon in 2019.

Who's who: Vibhu Paudyal

The digital revolution: Supporting clinical pharmacy through e-health, digital support systems, big data and more!

ESCP Research Committee Workshop

“International collaboration in designing and conducting research studies”

Research activities in clinical pharmacy are crucial for development of clinical pharmacy as a scientific and clinical field.

They enable new evidence to be obtained on efficacy and safety of medications and clinical pharmacy interventions in various settings of care and on various patient groups. In addition, measuring quality indicators, to cross-sectionally compare differences in provision of clinical pharmacy services (in different countries, regions, facilities, departments, etc.), to describe outcomes and pharmacoeconomic issues, etc.

Research in clinical pharmacy enhances the implementation of clinical pharmacy practice, particularly in countries where such services are still developing.

Research Committee of the ESCP under the umbrella of the ESCP announces annually the competition for the ESCP Grant Award in order to financially support the best clinical pharmacy research project held in international cooperation that helps to develop clinical pharmacy practice or clinical pharmacy research.

There are also different possibilities for financing of clinical pharmacy research through different European or country-specific grant agencies. However, such

opportunities are not yet fully used by some practicing clinical pharmacists and research is sometimes understood as “being accessible only to researchers, not practitioners”.

To strengthen involvement of clinical pharmacists in applications for different grant proposals at national and international levels, the ESCP Research Committee is organising during the 48th European Symposium on Clinical Pharmacy in Ljubljana, Slovenia (23-25 October 2019) a workshop entitled “International Collaboration in Designing and Conducting Research Studies”.

This workshop will be held by RESC members - Assoc. Prof. Daniela Fialová, PharmD, Ph.D., Assoc. Prof. Betül Okuyan, PharmD, Ph.D. (WS moderators) and Vicechair of the RESC Committee Ass. Prof. Vibhu Paudyal, PharmD, Ph.D. (WS convenor).

It will aim at improving participants’ knowledge of requirements for conducting international research projects and will emphasise the ESCP as an important platform for sharing research experience and for preparing and realising research projects in international collaboration. Several examples of scientific projects will be discussed, among the others including the EUROAGEISM FIP7 H2020 program focus-

ing on rational geriatric pharmacotherapy and development of clinical pharmacy services for older patients in Central and Eastern Europe. The aim of this workshop is also to review existing experience in international research, promote networking of early stage researchers and senior researchers by providing opportunities to share their research ideas and knowledge on barriers and enablers of successful research cooperation.

Among participants at this workshop will cordially welcome early stage researchers as well as researchers at different stages of their research career in order to discuss priorities and possible future proposals for international research collaboration.

This workshop has been supported by the European Society of Clinical Pharmacy and the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program EUROAGEISM H2020 under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 764632.

Daniela Fialová (Czech Republic)
fialovad@faf.cuni.cz
Betül Okuyan (Turkey)
betulokuyan@yahoo.com
ESCP RESC Committee

ESCP life

3

Evidence-based practice is fundamental to the development and delivery of safe and effective healthcare.

Systematic reviews, which refer to approaches to reducing bias and errors through systematic identification, appraisal and synthesis of relevant evidence on a specific topic (<http://www.cochrane-handbook.org/>), can help to provide cumulative, high quality evidence to inform evidence-based practice.

Systematic reviews are considered to provide the highest level of evidence within the hierarchy of evidence.

Pharmacists can benefit from gaining exper-

ience of the processes involved in undertaking, reporting and interpreting published systematic reviews.

The application of findings from systematic reviews can help to bridge evidence gaps and inform current clinical practice.

Other great reasons to attend include:

- Getting practical advice on conducting a systematic review
- Working with illustrative examples
- Opportunity to discuss with leading researchers
- Networking with colleagues from other countries

The Masterclass will cater to researchers

who are new to systematic reviews and those who are currently undertaking one. It will be delivered in an interactive format of plenary lectures, group work and discussions.

It is aimed at anyone currently involved or wishing to be involved in systematic reviews, irrespective of experience.

Cathal Cadogan (Ireland)
cathalcadogan@rcsi.ie
Angie Hazen (United Kingdom)
ankiehazen@hotmail.com
Vibhu Paudyal (United Kingdom)
v.paudyal@bham.ac.uk
ESCP RESC Committee

Masterclass on the “Fundamentals of systematic reviews of clinical pharmacy innovations”

State of the Art in Anticoagulation Therapy Challenges and opportunities for pharmacists

The 2019 ESCP International Workshop took place on 17 and 18 May in the cosmopolitan city of Antwerp focussing on anticoagulation therapy fully submerging participants during these two days in the risks and benefits as well as the challenges and opportunities associated with this particular medication class. With over 80 participants from 15 countries, this workshop truly took place in an international context. ESCP organised this workshop in successful collaboration with the Royal Pharmaceutical Society of Antwerp (KAVA) who provided their new congress centre in the heart of the city for this event.

Highlights of the plenary sessions

Day 1 started with a great lecture by **Thomas Vanassche**, cardiologist from the University Hospitals Leuven, Belgium, taking us on a trip from the origins of anticoagulant therapy to the latest developments. Remarkable statements were that coagulation is essential in survival but at the same time the n°1 killer, and that pharmacists are the most important partners for both physicians and patients to prevent mortality and disability in a safe and effective way.

Helen Williams, consultant pharmacist and national clinical adviser for atrial fibrillation (AF) in the UK, gave the second inspiring lecture of the day about 'The Pharmacist's role in delivering excellence in anticoagulation care to address unmet needs'. It became apparent that an important percentage of AF patients (21%) are undiagnosed in England, likely resulting in 14,700 avoidable strokes, and there are no factors to believe that it would be better across Europe, maybe even on the contrary. However, an ambitious national cardiovascular programme was launched in the UK to tackle these unmet needs by triangulation of strategic objectives, patient & public awareness, and clinical goals. In all three aspects, pharmacists are ideally placed to lead on delivering excellence in anticoagulation care.

The kick-off for the second day was given by **Isabelle Arnet** from the Pharmaceutical Care Research Group in Basel, Switzerland. As a recognized adherence expert, she brought up the challenging question how much adherence is enough. The answer depends on several parameters, such as the PK of the substance, and can be summarised in the concept of forgiveness. As people balance risks and benefits in light of their personal beliefs, it is of importance to take patients' preferences into consideration, e.g., regarding the choice between VKA and DOAC.

The last lecture was given by **Sotiris Antoniou**, consultant pharmacist for cardiovascu-

lar disease at Barts Health NHS Trust in the UK and chair of iPACT, the international Pharmacist for Anticoagulation Care Taskforce. He clearly explained the vision and mission of iPACT to (1) support the development of international evidence-based, patient-centred guidance for pharmaceutical care in anticoagulation; (2) develop and implement guidelines, tools and methods; (3) ensure the effective, safe and responsible use of anticoagulants, and (4) support adherence. As many medication errors occur because of poor communication between care settings, medication reconciliation and medication review are of utmost importance, which is one of the 18 formulated recommendations in the recently published iPACT interprofessional guideline to support patients receiving anticoagulation therapy.

Highlights of the workshops

All workshops were well attended and led vividly by the moderators using real life clinical cases.

Workshop DOAC, what the FAQ?

This workshop given by **Aris Prins** (KNMP, Netherlands) and **Silas Rydant** (KAVA, Belgium) started with a general overview of all the DOACs available on the European market, followed by clinical and practical differences between DOAC and VKA therapy. The importance of correct dosing, potential dangers of over- and underdosing as well as relevant factors to be considered when reviewing these medications were discussed. Up to 25% of patients don't take the correct dose of a direct oral anticoagulant as recommended. This under- or overdosing could lead to a higher risk of stroke or bleeding. Participants who attended the workshop were given practice-oriented schemes, tables, tips&tricks and other relevant resources to change their practice.

Workshop Anticoagulation – When things go wrong! - Prevention and management of bleeding with warfarin and DOACs

The workshop given by **Helen Williams** and **Sotiris Antoniou** focused on the risk of bleeding on warfarin and DOACs. The evidence from clinical studies and real world data was reviewed in relation to the bleeding risk. Participants were introduced to the use of various bleeding risk scores and had to review case studies where the bleeding risk had to be quantified and modifiable risk factors for bleeding needed to be addressed. The second part of the workshop dealt with the management of adverse effects with warfarin and DOACs, focusing specifically on active bleedings and strategies to manage mild, moderate and

life-threatening bleeds, including the use of reversal agents.

Workshop Mastering drug-drug interactions with oral anticoagulants and understanding the value of DOAC monitoring to optimise treatment

Workshop moderators **Anne-Laure Sennesael** and **Anne Spinewine**, both from the Universit Catholique de Louvain, Belgium, also found an ideal mix between theory and educational patient cases. Their main take home messages were that (1) drug-drug interactions are highly prevalent in patients taking oral anticoagulants, possibly affecting drug efficacy and patient safety; (2) aspirin prescription should be reappraised in patients taking VKA or DOAC, as it often has no valid indication and increases bleeding risk by 50%; (3) the clinical context of the patient must be taken into consideration when assessing the relevance of DOAC pharmacokinetics interactions; (4) measurement of DOAC anticoagulant intensity remains useful in common clinical situations (e.g. emergency surgery, thrombolysis, suspected drug accumulation), and (5) commercial specific assays are currently available for all DOAC, but should be implemented in daily practice to improve patient management.

Workshop Management of anticoagulation therapy in complex hospitalized patients

This workshop was provided by **Charlotte Quintens** and **Lorenz Van der Linden**, both from the UZ Leuven, a large Belgian teaching hospital. In a first part, they highlighted that oral anticoagulant use is mostly indicated by three clinical conditions: atrial fibrillation, venous thrombo-embolic disease and the use of mechanical valve prosthesis in valvular heart disease. Case fatality rates for these conditions were discussed and promotion of the correct use was emphasised using several patient cases (e.g. case- fatality rate of 5-9% in VTE, mainly due to pulmonary embolism exacerbated by right-sided heart failure). In a second part, the in-hospital periprocedural management of anticoagulants was discussed, with a large focus on DOACs. In sum, the lecturers advised interrupting DOAC use in nearly all situations (in the hospital), taking into account the bleeding risk of the procedure (and of the patient) as well as the pharmacokinetics of the involved DOAC. In most DOAC users undergoing a planned procedure, no low-molecular weight heparin bridging should be provided.

Stephane Steurbaut

ESCP secretary and workshop president
Stephane.Steurbaut@uzbrussel.be

From the Research Committee Highlights from IJCP

Translation and validation of a tool to assess the impact of clinical pharmacists' interventions (December 2018 issue)

Why it was done?

To validate the German version of the tool Clinical, Economic, and Organisational (CLEO) (termed CLEOde) and demonstrate feasibility of this tool in daily pharmacy practice at the hospital setting.

What was done?

The CLEO tool was translated from French into German (CLEOde) according to the ISPOR guidelines. For validation, ten clinical pharmacists assessed the potential relevance of all interventions (PIs) performed within 13 days of routine clinical pharmacy services of three Swiss hospitals in April and May 2016. Ten case models were used to evaluate interrater reliability and test-retest correlation. A 19-item questionnaire was applied to ten clinical pharmacists experienced with CLEOde and their agreement on appropriateness, acceptability, precision, and feasibility of the tool was evaluated.

What was found?

The interrater reliability was good for all dimensions except the organisational dimension, which was found poor.

The test-retest correlation was strong with excellent to fair reliability. The time needed for assessment was less than 1 minute per case. The use of CLEOde was seen as appropriate, acceptable, feasible, and precise by ten clinical pharmacists.

Conclusions

CLEOde is a validated tool to estimate the potential relevance of PIs in the German language. Although, there is need for refinement of the organisational dimension, this tool adds a qualitative value to PIs documentation.

What is interesting?

Pharmacists' Interventions (PIs) will be attributed to pharmacists' activities associated with patient care. There are classification systems to identify drug-related problems (DRPs) and planned PIs.

The tool CLEO (Clinical, Economic, and Organisational) was originally developed in French to assess the potential relevance of PIs in three dimensions. These are clinical (such as the patient-related outcomes),

economic (such as the current costs of therapy for the institution's perspective), and organisational outcomes (such as the process of care regarding the health care professionals) (<https://tel.archives-ouvertes.fr/tel-01315619/document>).

This tool will be used with existing classification systems for DRPs to obtain both qualitative and quantitative assessment of PIs. The present study confirmed the CLEOde as a validated tool.

The structured methodology approach of this study, including translation and validation, will be useful for pharmacy practice research.

Besides, this tool CLEOde determines qualitative value of PI documentation, this would be interesting for clinical pharmacists. Further studies will be conducted internationally after the tool CLEO is validated in English.

Betul Okuyan

on behalf of the Research Committee
betulokuyan@yahoo.com

Clinical pharmacy practice in the care of Chronic Kidney Disease patients: a systematic review (June 2019 issue)

Why it was done?

Clinical pharmacy (CP) services in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) have been provided for decades, however, new roles of CP are emerging, eg prescribing of medicines in these high-risk patients (CP services now implemented in the UK, USA and New Zealand). According to the last systematic literature review in 2012 (using peer-review articles published by 2010), information on the quality of provision of CP services in CKD patients was limited. The aim of this study was to systematically review new studies and critically appraise, synthesise and present available evidence on structures, processes and outcomes of CP services provided to CKD patients after 2010.

What was done?

International Pharmaceutical Abstracts (IPA), Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Medline, Scopus and Cochrane database were searched for peer reviewed papers published in English (March 2010 - December 2018). All controlled, uncontrolled and descriptive studies were assessed for quality using the validated mixed methods appraisal tool (MMAT) and controlled studies using Down's and Black's method. Studies and data were extracted by two independent

reviewers and synthesized according to structure, processes and outcomes of provided clinical pharmacy services.

What was found?

A total of 47 studies were included in the review. The majority (27) were uncontrolled studies (21 prospective, 6 retrospective), 10 were randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and 10 non-RCTs. Structures of provided clinical pharmacy services were poorly reported in all studies (only 2 studies presented details of multidisciplinary team involvement and 5 reported aspects of clinical pharmacists' training). All studies provided some description of the processes undertaken, however detailed information was lacking (the majority of studies reported medication chart reviews to identify any DRPs). Outcomes were described by 37 studies and mostly clinical outcomes were reported (e.g. improved blood pressure management, improved clinical lab tests-Hb levels, CrCl, PTH, calcium levels etc.). Only in a few studies were (7) humanistic and/or economic outcomes measured.

Conclusions

While new possibilities for strengthening the role of clinical pharmacists in multidisciplinary

teams caring for patients with CKD are emerging (e.g. complex medication management and medication prescribing), quality evidence for wider implementation of new services is lacking.

Generally, published studies on clinical pharmacy provision and its' outcomes in patients with CKD are of low quality and of insufficient volume. Even if controlled studies in this systematic review showed that pharmacist interventions improved some clinical outcomes, humanistic and economic outcomes were insufficiently studied. More high-quality research in this area is needed.

What is interesting

High-quality evidence may support extending the roles of clinical pharmacists in different countries and settings of care through identification of any (even non-significant) drug-related problems to taking full responsibility for complex medication management (even in high-risk patients, e.g. patients with CKD) or even in medication prescribing for high-risk patients.

Vibhu Paudyal (United Kingdom)
v.paudyal@bham.ac.uk
ESCP RESC Committee

With the increasing attention for the role of the pharmaceutical industry in promoting opioids as analgesics, this group of medicines has almost come into disrepute and there is a wave of insinuations being pushed through all kinds of political advisers and interest groups. How correct are all the assumptions? Is the famous pain-ladder of WHO indeed corrupted by outside influences? What should the role of opioids in analgesia then be? The need for a more objective assessment of theory and practice is eminent.

In 2020, the International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy, the 'house journal' of ESCP, is

planning to publish a special issue themed 'Pain management in the opioid addiction era', in 2020. Prof. Janie Sheridan (Auckland, New Zealand) will assist the editorial team in compiling the issue and in critically appraising the contributions. The other editors for this issue will be the two associate editors, Dr. Vibhu Paudyal, Dr. Yolande Hanssens and the IJCP Editor-in-chief.

We invite all colleagues to contribute to this special issue. Commentaries and reviews are welcome, but also reports of all study designs including randomised controlled trials, observational studies, database analyses, cross sectional and qualitative

Special Issue IJCP: Pain management and opioids.

Call for submissions

studies within the scope of pain management with opioids, or its relation with addiction.

The deadline for submission 20th December 2019, but we welcome submissions before that date. The special issue and an editorial will be compiled when all contributions have been accepted for publication. Please let me know if you want to contribute, what type of article and the title or topic before the end of 30 September 2019.

Foppe van Mil
IJCP Editor-in-chief
jwfvml@ijcp-editor.org

Metamizole medicines: harmonising in europe (EMA Dec. 2018)

Metamizole (also known as dipyrrone) is an analgesic medicine (painkiller) that can also relieve fever and muscle spasm. It has been used for many decades in the EU by mouth, as suppositories or by injection, to treat severe pain and fever that cannot be controlled with other treatments.

A review was carried out by EMA's human medicines committee (CHMP) at the request of Poland, which was concerned by the substantial differences in the recommendations on the use of metamizole in different EU countries, given that it is known the medicine may occasionally cause severe side effects, such as effects on the blood.

EMA's recommendations include setting a maximum single dose by mouth of 1,000 mg, taken up to 4 times daily (a maximum daily dose of 4,000 mg), in patients from 15 years of age. Treatment should start at the lowest recommended dose and only be increased if needed.

If given by injection the total daily dose should not exceed 5,000 mg. Doses in younger patients should be based on their body weight but some products may be unsuitable because of their strength.

Although metamizole has been on the market for nearly a century, evidence of its effects in pregnancy and breastfeeding is scarce.

The review found little to suggest problems in early pregnancy, and single doses in the

first 6 months might be acceptable if other analgesics cannot be used. However, there is some evidence of effects on the kidneys and circulation of the foetus if the medicine is used in the last 3 months of pregnancy, and the medicine should therefore not be used in this period. As a precaution, metamizole should not be used during breastfeeding because the infant may receive high amounts of the medicine in the milk relative to the infant's weight. The CHMP opinion will now be forwarded to the European Commission, which will issue a final legally binding decision applicable in all EU Member States.

Omega-3 fatty acids questioned

Omega 3-fatty acid medicines contain the fatty acids eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) commonly found in fish oils.

Omega-3 fatty acid medicines have been authorised for use after a heart attack, in combination with other medicines, in several EU countries since 2000, at a dose of 1 g per day. At the time of their authorisation, available data showed some benefits in reducing serious problems with the heart and blood vessels, although the benefits were considered modest. Further data that have become available since then have not confirmed the beneficial effects of these medicines for this use.

As a result of the investigation the message underneath is addressed to healthcare professionals.

- Omega-3 fatty acid medicines will no longer be authorised for secondary prevention after myocardial infarction.
- This is based on a review of all the available data on the efficacy of omega-3 fatty acid medicines in this indication.
- The review looked at results of the open-label 'GISSI Prevenzione' study performed in 1999 which supported the initial authorisation of these medicines, as well as retrospective cohort studies, more recent randomised controlled trials and results of meta-analyses.
- The review concluded that, while a small relative risk reduction was seen in the original open label GISSI Prevenzione study, such beneficial effects were not confirmed in more recent randomised controlled trials.
- This review does not affect the authorisation of omega-3 fatty acid medicines for the treatment of hypertriglyceridaemia. The review of omega-3 fatty acid medicines was started on 22 March 2018 at the request of the Swedish medicines agency. The review has been carried out by the Committee for Medicinal Products for Human Use (CHMP), responsible for questions concerning medicines for human use, which has adopted the Agency's opinion. The CHMP opinion will now be forwarded to the European Commission, which will issue a final legally binding decision applicable in all EU Member States.

EMA news

Gert Laekeman
ESCP Past President
gert.laekeman@kuleuven.be

Scientific Committee

Alenka Kovacic, Chair	Vibhu Paudyal
Nejc Horvat	Brian Addison
Bart van den Bemt	Mitja Kos
Maja Petre	Monika Lutters

The conference theme “The Digital Revolution: supporting clinical pharmacy through e-health, digital support systems, big data and more.” will be realised via subthemes for each day of the conference to which the plenary sessions are aligned.

The conference has been designed to provide an innovative and comprehensive overview of the latest technology developments in clinical pharmacy. We believe that both scientists and practitioners will find the programme beneficial for further implementation of digital aids in their daily practice.

Digitalisation of clinical pharmacy enables development of new services, support systems and faster and easier data collecting, but we must also be aware of new risks use of technology brings. Over the course of three days the congress will feature plenary lectures, keynote sessions, parallel workshops and abstract presentations with aim of illuminating current challenges, potential solutions and way forward with help of technology.

During the symposium, the following topics will be presented through plenary lectures and workshops:

- clinical decision support systems,
- big data and clinical pharmacy,
- e-health to support medication adherence,
- computer assisted medication verification,
- digital support for therapeutic drug monitoring,
- new technologies for clinical pharmacy education.

Wednesday 23th – Digital transformation and direct patient care

- o Digital transformation, what is all about (Mitja Kos)
- o New wave of digitalisation in the Estonian health services industry (Karl Henrik Peterson)
- o Use of mobile devices to support clinical pharmacy (Filipa Costa)
- o Apps and aids for adherence (Bart Pouls)
- o mHealth intervention to support asthma self-management: evaluation and implementation (Ellen Koster)

Thursday 24th – Tools to support clinical pharmacy and clinical decision support systems

- o Detection of drug related problems by automated screening of patients’ electronic medical records: a tool for the clinical pharmacist? (Veerle Voulon)
- o Computer assisted Medication Reconciliation (Victor Huiskes)
- o Computer-assisted TDM – a low-hanging fruit for the clinical pharmacist (Polonca Drogenik)

48th ESCP Symposium
25 October 2019, Ljubljana (Slovenia)

The digital revolution: Supporting clinical pharmacy through e-health, digital support systems, big data and more!

- o Pharmacovigilance support systems: How to Classify Severity and How to Establish Causality? (Monika Sonc)
- o Clinical decision support systems in clinical practice (Barbara Maats)
- o Impact of Clinical decision support systems on clinical/economical outcomes.
- o New legal/safety risks due to the introduction of clinical decision support systems (Pieter Cornu).

Friday 25th – Big data

- Four plenaries will address this sub-theme:
- o Big data: challenges for clinical practice (Amitava Banerjee)
 - o Big data: challenges for research (Samuel Allemam)
 - o Future digital possibilities for clinical pharmacists (Jurrian van Rijswijk)
 - o Supporting clinical pharmacy education: use of avatars for education (Stephen Chapman).

During the symposium 20 different workshops will be held in 33 slots. Also oral communications and poster discussions will be held from Wednesday to Friday.

Symposium venue - Cankarjev dom is Slovenia's largest cultural institution close to the symposium hotel and within easy reach of the city centre and other accommodation.

On 22nd October 2019 at ESCP Symposium venue, Cankarjev Dom, Ljubljana, a Masterclass will be held. The pre-conference masterclass offers a unique opportunity for participants to attend a one day, in-depth training and workshop session on a research, education or clinical topic delivered by leading international experts. Moderators Dr. Cathal Cadogan, Dr. Ankie Hazen and Dr. Vibhu Paudyal will present fundamentals of systematic reviews of clinical pharmacy innovations.

The Symposium Evening Lecture will be held on Tuesday evening. The title of this year’s lecture is ‘Pharmacists and Emotional Intelligence’ and will be presented by Željko Čurić, a psychiatrist, psychotherapist and an innovative speaker. His lectures are always a special experience.

Alenka Kovačič
Chair of the 48th ESCP Symposium
alenka.kovacic@sb-ms.si

January 2019
Workshop submission call

3 April 2019
Workshop proposal
deadline

4 March 2019
Abstract submission

29 April 2019
Abstract submission
deadline

1 April 2019
Online registration opening

30 July 2019
End of early bird
registration

22 October 2019
Preconference

To learn more about the programme and register, visit:

www.escpweb.org

or mail

info@escpweb.org

For Your Diary

2019

23-25 October

Ljubljana
(Slovenia)

48th European Symposium on Clinical Pharmacy:
“The Digital Revolution: Supporting clinical pharmacy through e-health, digital support systems, big data and more!”

Announcements

Everybody is talking about “Artificial Intelligence” (AI).

The new book by pharmacist **Claudia Rijken** offers a refreshing new perspective: How to combine the possibilities of technology with the human factor in pharmaceutical care – replacing the A in AI with “Apothecary” instead of “Artificial”. After working in community pharmacy, Claudia gradually moved into a digital innovation role within Novartis and recently founded two companies around digital pharmaceutical care. In “Pharmaceutical Care in Digital Revolution”, the editor and co-authors **Paul Iske, Rob Peters, Barry Meesters, Wilma Göttgens, and Paul Rulkens** aim to pave the way to “circular pharmaceutical care”.

The book draws an analogy between the digital forests of opportunities and our biological forest ecosystems. The comparison between the destabilis-

How „Apothecary Intelligence“ could improve pharmaceutical care Pharmaceutical Care in Digital Revolution: Insights towards Circular Innovation

Edited by **Claudia Rijken**

ing impact of human activity on earth’s ecosystems and the potentially disruptive impact of technology on current healthcare systems creates a sense of urgency: Now is the time to act, before the ecosystems – both biological and technological – spin out of control.

The solution proposed by Claudia and her co-authors is to create “blended care models: digital if possible, human where needed”. This requires the evolution of pharmacy from a STEM to a STEM+ education by putting more emphasis on humanistic and social expertise and digital pharma literacy. At the same time, value-driven pharmaceutical care should be “digital by design” and built on a “Single Point of Truth (SPOT) platform for medication information, which should be the basis for all digital derivatives”.

Organized in four parts and with chapters titled “Oxygen required” or “Ethical practice: Fostering trees of life”, the

book paints a landscape of current challenges, digital health innovations, conditions for enhancing pharmaceutical care through the use of digital innovation, and inspiration on the development of innovative digital pharmaceutical care pathways in daily practice. Designed as a practical resource, it not only explains how AI “can support trend analysis and decision making that augment pharmaceutical care expertise.” It also contains a rich diversity of links to additional resources, illustrative videos (through QR-codes), and tutorials on how to get started in practice.

This book makes sure to remind the reader of what pharmaceutical care in digital revolution is about: “Blending human and digital pharmaceutical care to establish apothecary intelligence.”

Samuel Allemann

samuel.allemann@pharmasuisse.org

Normal Membership	2019
1 year Full Membership	€ 90
3 years Full Member ship	€ 230
5 years Full Membership	€ 360
Student Membership	€ 25

Dual Membership (SFPC/SUFO)	2019
1 year Full Membership	€ 75
3 years Full Member ship	€ 190
Student Membership	€ 20

ESCP

1979 – 2019

European Society of Clinical Pharmacy

ESCP News is published by ESCP

Editor: Marie Caroline Husson (France)
Page Lay-out: Corinne Tollier (France)
Language editing: Ian Millar (UK)

ESCP International Office

SIR Institute for Pharmacy Practice and Policy
Theda Mansholtstraat 5b - NL-2331 JE Leiden - The Netherlands
Tel: +31 71 5766157
E-mail: international.office@escpweb.org
www.escpweb.org

Deadline for the submission of material:
for issue number 185 is 15th September 2019.

*The contents of this publication are compiled in good faith.
The publisher accepts no responsibility for omissions or errors.*